

Studies on the Synthesis and Spectral Properties of Various *p*-Anisylated Quinazolinones

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Syntheses of 1-(*p*-methoxyphenyl)-1H-quinazolin-4-one (I), 2(*p*-methoxyphenyl)-3H-quinazolin-4-one (VI), 3-(*p*-methoxyphenyl)-3H-quinazolin-4-one (VII) and 4-(*p*-methoxyphenyl)-1H-quinazolin-2-one (VIII) have been achieved and their spectral properties (UV, IR, NMR) have been studied. I and VIII are new compounds, During this investigation it has been observed that the product obtained from condensation of II with formamide is represented by the structure III and not I, as previously reported.²

A general route¹ to the synthesis of 1-alkyl-1H-quinazolin-4-ones is the condensation of formamide with appropriate alkyl substituted anthranilic acid. Mukherjee *et al*² extended this method to the synthesis of 1-aryl substituted quinazolin-4-ones by using a higher reaction temperature, presumably due to the poor reactivity of the lone pair of electrons of the nitrogen of the diphenylamine system, and claimed the synthesis of 1-(*p*-methoxyphenyl)-1H-quinazolin-4-one (I) by condensation of *N*-(*p*-methoxyphenyl)-anthranilic acid (II) and formamide.

Repetition of the experiment performed by Mukherjee *et al* furnished in our hands a mixture of three products (Chart I), the major one of which was found to be identical in all respects (m.p., m.m.p. UV, IR, NMR) with the compound* believed to have the formulation I. Surprisingly, however, the spectral properties of this compound was found to be quite different from those expected for I and also from those reported for 1-phenyl-1H-quinazolin-4-one systems³ and this discrepancy led us to carry out structural investigation

Fig. 1. UV Spectra of III and V.

FIG. 1

FIG. 2

1. N. J. Leonard and William, V. Ruyle, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1948, **13**, 903.
2. S. Somasckhara, G. M. Shah and S. L. Mukherjee, *Curr. Sci.*, 1964, **33**, 521.

*Authentic sample was kindly supplied by Dr. S. L. Mukherjee, Sarabhai Chemicals, Baroda for direct comparison,

of this compound. The mass spectrometrically derived molecular weight, 254, elemental analysis and NMR proton count (14H), settled its molecular formula as $C_{15}H_{14}N_2O_2$ and not $C_{15}H_{12}N_2O_2$ as assigned to I by Mukherjee *et al*². These data in conjunction with the facts that (i) the UV spectrum (Fig. 1) of the compound is more akin to that of 2-(*p*-methoxyanilino)-benzamide rather than that of 1-phenyl-1H-quinazolin-4-one system³; (ii) its IR spectrum shows a strong-NH absorption band at 3226 cm^{-1} ; and (iii) its NMR spectrum (Fig. 2) lacks the low field C-2 proton signal³⁻⁴ of quinazolin-4-ones and instead exhibits a two-proton signal at 5.25 a chemical shift expected from the- CH_2 -protons of a methylenediamino system firmly established the structure of the compound as 1-(*p*-methoxyphenyl)-1,2,3,4-tetrahydroquinazolin-4-one (III). The mass spectrum of the compound which shows characteristic peaks at $M-29$, and at m/e 210 and m/e 182 presumably due to the sequential expulsion of the groups- $CH_2=NH$,- CH_3 and- $\overset{\cdot}{C}O$ is also consistent with the formulation III.

The formation of III by condensation of N-(*p*-methoxyphenyl)-anthranilic acid and formamide is rather unusual and is obviously a result of reduction of the intermediate

3. H. M. Blatter, H. Lukaszewski and G. deStevens, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1965, **30**, 1020.

4. S. C. Pakrashi, J. Bhattacharyya, L. F. Johnson and H. Budzikiewicz, *Tetrahedron*, 1963, **19**, 1011.

I by hydride transfer from formamide molecules⁵. That such reduction does really take place by formamide received experimental verification. Quinazolinone** I, arising out of condensation of 2- (*p*-methoxyanilino)-benzamide with ethyl orthoformate, furnished the corresponding dihydro derivative (III) as the sole product when heated with formamide at 170-80°.

It would be pertinent to mention here that though several methods^{3,6} for the synthesis of 1-aryl-1H-quinazolin-4-ones with substituents in 2-position have been reported in the literature, no suitable method other than the one² cited above, and subsequently proved to be erroneous is available for the synthesis of 2-unsubstituted N₁-aryl-quinazolin-4-ones. The compound I has now been synthesised by us and it is a new quinazoline derivative obtained as a granular solid, m.p. 186-88°. The elemental analysis of this compound, its mass-spectrometrically derived molecular weight, 252 and its NMR proton count (12H), all corresponded to a molecular formula, C₁₅H₁₂N₂O₂. Its ultraviolet absorption characteristics (Fig. 3: $\lambda_{\text{max}}^{\text{EtOH}}$ 235, 280, 304, 314 m μ : log ϵ 4.47, 3.88, 4.08, 4.00) are comparable to those reported for 1-phenyl-2-methyl-1H-quinazolin-4-one³ and its IR spectrum, as expected, lacks any absorption in the-NH, -OH region and shows an intense band at 1642 cm⁻¹ for -CH=N-C=O system. The four aromatic protons of the anisyl moiety resonated at 7.20 and 7.49 δ ($J=8.5$ c/s) as a typical A₂B₂ quartet and the proton at C-2 and the one peri to the carbonyl showed signals at 8.33 and 8.38 δ respectively in the NMR spectrum.

Name of the Compound	Structure	UV $\lambda_{\text{max}}^{\text{EtOH}}$ in m μ (log ϵ)
1-(<i>p</i> -methoxyphenyl)- 1H-quinazolin-4-one		235 (4.47) 280 (3.88) 304 (4.08) 314 (4.0)
2-(<i>p</i> -methoxyphenyl)- 3H-quinazolin-4-one		297 (4.19)

5. E. C. Taylor and E. E. Garcia, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1964, **86**, 4721.

6. M. R. Uskokovic, J. Jacobelli and W. Wenner, Abstract, 147th National Meeting of A. C. S., Philadelphia, Pa, April 1964, p. 7M.

**Condensation of II with formamide in presence of POCl₃ was also found to produce I in addition to 3-methoxy-9-chloroacridine, 3-methoxyacridone and 2-(*p*-methoxyanilino)-benzamide (V).

3-(*p*-methoxyphenyl)-
3H-quinazolin-4-one

230 (4.72)
266 (4.2)
303 (3.75)
312 (3.69)

4-(*p*-methoxyphenyl)-
1-H-quinazolin-2-one

228 (4.46)
277 (3.72)
322 (3.8)

Fig. 3. UV Spectra of I, VI, VII and VIII.

FIG. 3

A comparative study of the various spectral properties of different *p*-methoxyphenylated quinazolinones was made with a view to finding out the contribution of anisyl substituent in different positions at the pyrimidine nucleus of the quinazoline moiety towards the modification of the spectral data. Compounds VI, VII and VIII were prepared (*vide* experimental) and their important spectral characteristics studied. It would be interesting to find that the IR and NMR spectral properties of these compounds are grossly similar though their UV absorption spectra (Table I) are quite different and, as such, may be regarded as diagnostic.

EXPERIMENTAL

General : The melting points were determined on the Kofler block and were uncorrected. The ultraviolet absorption spectra were measured in 95% ethanol, the infrared spectra on KBr disc, unless otherwise stated. The analytical samples were dried at 80° over P₂O₅ for 24 hr. in vacuo. Anhydrous sodium sulphate was used for drying organic solvents and for column chromatography Brockmann alumina was used throughout.

N-*p*-(*methoxyphenyl*)-*anthranilic acid* (II) : *N*-(*p*-methoxyphenyl)-anthranilic acid was prepared by Ullmann condensation of *o*-chlorobenzoic acid with *p*-anisidine in presence of anhydrous potassium carbonate and activated copper powder. The product was crystallised from methanol as pale yellow needles, m.p. 182-3°, ν_{\max} 3278, 2985, 2597, 1652 and 900 cm⁻¹, $\frac{\text{EtOH}}{\lambda_{\max}}$ 288 (log ϵ , 3.97) and 333 m μ (log ϵ , 3.54) and NMR (CDCl₃) δ 3.68 (s, 3H), 6.02-7.28 (m, 8H), 7.66 (d, 1H, J=6c/s) and 8.60 (NH, W_H=12 c/s). (Found : C, 69.20; H, 5.27; N, 5.80; O, 19.89. Calc. for C₁₄H₁₃NO₃ : C, 69.13; H, 5.35; N, 5.76; O, 19.75%).

2-(*p*-*methoxyanilino*)-*benzamide* (V) : 2-(*p*-methoxyanilino)-benzamide was synthesised according to the method of Blatter *et al.*³, starting from II. The crude solid was crystallised from methanol as yellow needles, m.p. 128-30°, ν_{\max} 3508, 3322, 1669 cm⁻¹ and NMR (CDCl₃) δ 3.82 (s, 3H), 6.42 (NH₂, W_H=20 c/s), 6.56-7.60 (m, 8H) and 9.5 (NH, W_H=15c/s) (Found : M⁺ 242; C, 69.61; H, 5.97; N, 11.58; O, 13.54. Calc. for C₁₄H₁₄O₂N₂ : C, 69.42; H, 5.78; N, 11.56; O, 13.22%).

1-(*p*-*methoxyphenyl*)-1,2,3,4 *tetrahydroquinazolin-4-one* (III):—Compound II was heated with 3-4 equivalents of formamide in a sealed tube at 150-60° for 4 hr. following exactly the method reported by Mukherjee *et al.*² The residue was chromatographed. 4-Methoxydiphenylamine (IV), obtained from the earlier fractions of the petrol ether eluate, crystallised from petrol ether as white needles (32% yield), m.p. 104-5° (lit.⁷ m.p. 105°). Later fractions of the petrol ether eluate furnished pale yellow needles (22% yield), m.p. 130° from benzene as it was found to be identical in all respects (m.p., mm.p., UV, IR, NMR) with V. The major product (III), obtained from the chloroform eluate, crystallised from methanol in white rods (35% yield), m.p. 186°. (Found M⁺ 254; C, 70.27; H, 5.73; N, 10.91; O, 12.82. Calc. for C₁₅H₁₄O₂N₂, C, 70.86; H, 5.51; N, 11.02; O, 12.59%).

1-(*p*-*methoxyphenyl*)-1*H*-*quinazolin-4-one* (I): (a) A mixture of 2-(*p*-methoxy anilino) benzamide (0.5 g) and ethylorthoformate (5 ml) in diethylene glycol (5 ml) was heated at 120° for 15 hr. Excess of ethyl orthoformate was removed under reduced pressure and the residue was taken in chloroform and extracted with 5N HCl. Acid extract was basified with ammonia and extracted with ether. Ether extract was washed, dried and distilled. The residue crystallised from acetone as white granules (0.3 g), m.p. 186-88°. (Found : M⁺ 252; C, 71.29; H, 4.88; N, 11.34; O, 12.99. Calc. for C₁₅H₁₂O₂N₂ : C, 71.42; H, 4.76; N, 11.11; O, 12.69%)

(b) A solution of V (0.5 g) in formic acid (10 ml) was heated in a sealed tube at 110-20° for 24 hr. Excess formic acid was removed under reduced pressure and worked up as before. The crude product was chromatographed. The solid, obtained from the benzene-chloroform

(1:1) eluate, crystallised from acetone as white granules (0.06 g), m.p. 186-88°. It was found to be identical in all respects (m.p., m.m.p., TLC, UV, IR, NMR) with I.

Conversion of I to III: Compound I was heated with 6-8 equivalents of formamide at 170-80° for 5 hr. Excess formamide was removed under reduced pressure and the residue was crystallised from methanol as white rods (92% yield), m.p. 186°. It was found to be identical with III in all respects (m.p., m.m.p., TLC, UV, IR, NMR).

2-(p-methoxyphenyl)-1H-quinazolin-4-one (VI): An intimate mixture of anthranilamide (1.13 g) and anisic acid (1.3 g) was heated at 190° for 4 hr. The reaction mixture was chromatographed. The chloroform eluate on concentration gave a solid which was crystallised from methanol as white needles (1.0 g), m.p. 245-46°, (lit.⁸, m.p. 247°), ν_{\max} 1666 and 1589 cm^{-1} , $\lambda_{\max}^{\text{EtOH}}$ 297 $\text{m}\mu$ ($\log \epsilon$, 4.19); NMR (CF_3COOH) δ 3.63 (s, 3H), 6.96 (d, 2H, $J=9.0$ c/s), 7.65 (m, 3H) 7.82 (d, 2H, $J=9.0$ c/s) and 8.17 (doublet of doublets, $J_1=8.5$ c/s, $J_2=2$ c/s). (Found: M^+ 252; C, 71.56; H, 4.65; N, 11.29; O, 13.00. Calc. for $\text{C}_{15}\text{H}_{12}\text{O}_2\text{N}_2$: C, 71.42; H, 4.76; N, 11.11; O, 12.69%).

3-(p-methoxyphenyl)-3H-quinazolin-4-one (VII): Molar proportion of N-formyl-*p*-anisidine and anthranilic acid was heated at 150-60° for 1 hr. The crude solid crystallised from alcohol as white needles (70% yield), m.p. 193° (Lit.⁹ m.p. 190-1°) ν_{\max} 1697 and 1626 cm^{-1} , $\lambda_{\max}^{\text{EtOH}}$ 230 ($\log \epsilon$, 4.72), 266 ($\log \epsilon$, 4.2) 303 ($\log \epsilon$ 3.75) and 312 $\text{m}\mu$ ($\log \epsilon$, 3.69) and NMR (CDCl_3) δ 3.90 (s, 3H), 7.05 (d, 2H, $J=9.0$ c/s), 7.37 (d, 2H, $J=9.0$ c/s), ca 7.76 (m, 3H), 8.12 (s, 1H) and 8.40 (doublet of doublets, $J_1=7.5$ c/s, $J_2=2$ c/s). (Found: M^+ 252; C, 70.99; H, 4.61; N, 11.54; O, 12.87. Calc. for $\text{C}_{15}\text{H}_{12}\text{O}_2\text{N}_2$: C, 71.42; H, 4.76; N, 11.11; O, 12.69%).

4-(p-methoxyphenyl)-1H-quinazolin-2-one (VIII): 4-(*p*-methoxyphenyl)-1H-quinazolin-2-one was prepared by heating *O*-(*p*-methoxyphenyl)-aniline (synthesised according to the method of Ullmann and Bleier¹⁰ starting from anthranilic acid) with urea at 190-200° until the whole mass solidified (3 hr). The product crystallised from methanol as white needles (85% yield), m.p. 260°, ν_{\max} (Nujol) 1680 and 1600 cm^{-1} ; $\lambda_{\max}^{\text{EtOH}}$ 228 ($\log \epsilon$, 4.46), 277 ($\log \epsilon$, 3.72) and 322 $\text{m}\mu$ ($\log \epsilon$, 3.8) and NMR (DMSO) δ 3.95 (s, 3H), 7.22 (d, 2H, $J=9.0$ c/s), 7.78 (d, 2H, $J=9.0$ c/s) (Found: M^+ 252; C, 71.00; H, 4.31; N, 11.32; O, 12.77. Calc. for $\text{C}_{15}\text{H}_{12}\text{O}_2\text{N}_2$: C, 71.42; H, 4.76; N, 11.11; O, 12.69%).

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